

Decreasing Error Rate of k-NN for Data classification using Double weighted function

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ABSTARCT

A k-NN algorithm is a most compatible algorithm for large data set classification in data mining. k-NN algorithm is a most effective and simple technique. With a fast growth of online data, there is a need to classify that dataset into predefined class or category for managing and fast access point of view, is so complex task. k-NN is simple and effectively implemented for large dataset. but sometimes large dataset having sparseness, noisy, ambiguous or mislabeled points, which comes in k range value for classification, generate result as misclassification. In previous papers of single and dual weight k-NN algorithm, higher weight value given to top k data objects to avoid misclassification to reduce error rate in result. In this paper, we represent the reason behind this error and removed it by double weight function. Proposed algorithm smooth weight value path for top k data objects and it is helpful to decrease error rate compare to other algorithms. In this paper, proposed algorithm is proved by taking different k values for different dataset.

Key words: Classification, Query point, Voting, Nearest neighbour, Smooth weight value

INTRODUCTION

Data mining is a process that discovers patterns and relationship in data that may be used to make correct prediction using variety of data Analysis tools [1]. Data mining works in many area like Artificial Intelligence (AI), Image processing, Market Analysis using different pattern classification and recognition [2,3,4,8] etc.

A. Data Classification

For prediction of future class label or Variable value, there are two techniques respectively – Classification and Regression [2,5]. Data classification is a process between query point and training dataset to categorize query point. Using pre-labeled training dataset and classification algorithm, class label is assigned to new query point. Pre-labeled training dataset is taken from historical database of real world [6]. There are many data classification techniques exist like Decision Tree, Neural Network and Support Vector Machine etc. Among all, k-NN algorithm is simple and effective supervised algorithm for large dataset [7]. k-NN algorithm use all existing training datasets every time to classify new query point[3]. So it required more space to store all training dataset but give effective result. Here, k-NN algorithm is explained in details below.

B. k-NN algorithm

k-NN algorithm is a well known and widely used algorithm in many areas for classification which proposed by T.M. Cover and P.E. Hart[3]. k-NN is robust and good for large dataset among different classification techniques like Naïve Bayes, Neural Network, centroid-based approach, Decision tree, SVM, Rocchio Classifier, Regression Model, etc. [2,8,9,10]. The idea behind using k-NN for classification is that class label assign to a new unclassified data object. it is given by majority voting of its k nearest neighbor from training set. That means there are training set of data objects with class labels and distance calculated from unclassified data object with all data objects. Then distance is sorted in ascending order and top k distance data objects are selected. Considering majority voting of class label of k data objects, that label is assigned to new data object. Here majority voting means class with highest majority voting of k dataset is assigned to unclassified dataset. In case of tie for class label, k values need to be changed or randomly select any one class label [13].

k NN algorithm estimate class label from radius of region of all k data objects. That means the estimation is affected by the sensitivity of selection of the neighborhood size k, because the radius region is collection of all k data with sorted distance. if k values taken so small then local estimation become poor with little data objects in radius region if data property is sparseness, noisy, ambiguous or mislabeled points in local region and misclassification occur. And if k values taken as so large may be there are outliers comes into radius region and occur in misclassification result. Proposed algorithm work on second issue for large dataset that if k value is increase, error rate is also increase in simple k-NN algorithm. But proposed algorithm decrease error rate compare to our versions of k-NN algorithm. From figure- 1 we can understand the large k values problem.

Figure 1 Misclassification occurs if k value increases when dataset has outliers [11]

In figure -1, Diamond red color shape represent class 1 and Circle green color shape represent class 2. Test document in circle shape with blue color is need to assigned class label. If k=2 is selected then as per majority voting, class of test document is 2 that is right answer but if we increase k value and select k=6 then answer is class 1 that is misclassification. That shows that dominating class 1 is degrading accuracy of k-NN classifier for higher k value selection in large data. We can improve accuracy means decrease error rate of k-NN classifier [11]. Here, Basic k NN algorithm steps are defined:

- 1) Select the training set T and new data object x'.
- 2) Find the Euclidean distance between all T data objects and new data object x'.
- 3) Sort all the data objects in ascending order of distance means less distance to large distance. Here less distance means more closer data object to new data object.
- 4) Find a class label for new data object by majority voting of classes of top k data objects.

PREVIOUS WORK

Large k values of training set gives misclassification result but we can avoid it using weight. Jakub zavrel [12], Duhani [14] and jianping Gou [15] authors gave the concept of single weight and dual weight respectively.

In the proposed algorithm, After sorted data objects as per distance, top k data objects are selected and then they gave weight to each data objects from 1 to 0 in ascending order by no.

of equations. That means higher matching or more close data object get highest weight 1 or near to 1 and remaining is less than that unto 0. Weighted sum applied to all data objects that belong to same class and then majority voting performed based on higher weighted sum. Class label of highest weighted sum is assigned to new data object. This improved k NN algorithm steps are bellow:

- 1) Select the training data set T and new data object x'.
- 2) Find Euclidean distance between all T data objects and new data object x'.
- 3) Sort all the data objects in ascending order.
- 4) Compute the weight using single or dual weight function for all k data objects.
- 5) Find the sum of weights of data objects that are belong to same class.
- 6) Assign class label to new data object by finding highest weight class.

THE PROPOSED DOUBLE WEIGHTED k-NN

As shown in previous work when k values increase result is more improved then simple k NN algorithm. Rather there is some less accuracy get after using single and dual weight function compare to proposed work. In this proposed work, double weight function applied. In previous work, weight values of data objects are so varied in between 1 and 0 and no smooth weight values has been got data objects as closer to further data objects. so weighted sum and majority voting of highest weight is not proper calculated or misclassification may be there. But in this proposed work, more smooth weight value assigned to each data objects from closer to further data. So classification result will be more accurate. As exponent weight function of Shepard [16] of its distance. Here they assume α and β values 1.0 for experiment for generalization purpose.

$$w_j = e^{-\alpha d_j^\beta} \quad \text{Where } j=1, 2, \dots, k$$

In this proposed scheme, exponential weight function and Uniform weight function [17] is combined to get more smooth weight for each data object from more closer to further data objects. Using uniform weight, more close data object get high weight and increasing i values and in inverse form, weight is decreasing for other ascending data object. This uniform function with Shepard function gives smoother weight values. This is shown in results with comparative chart. Here, use of double weight function for classification is less influence with noise for large dataset. Following is uniform function,

$$w_i = \frac{1}{i} \quad i = 1, \dots, k$$

The proposed scheme use weight function,

$$W_i = e^{-\alpha d_i^\beta} \times \frac{1}{i}$$

Where α and β is 1.0 and $i=1,2,3,\dots,k$ data objects. Here $W_1=1$ when $k=1$ for near data object.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULT

A. Experiment Dataset:

In this section, for classification, error rate is most effective measure for performance evolution compare other algorithm. error rate means what is the probability of data objects get correctly identified with actual class after experiment. Here from the data set all data objects are taken as training set and testing set. In advance, training set has a class label and after testing they get new class labels. If actual and result class same then no error. But for

example 100 data objects have misclassified among 200 data objects then 50% error rate in it.

Dataset	Attributes	Instances	Classes
Glass	10	214	7
Ionosphere	34	351	2
vehicle	18	946	4

Table -1 Dataset taken from UCI Machine dataset

Some characteristics of UCI Machine dataset [18] in details listed in table-1 and table -2 represent how error rate is reduced in this proposed algorithm compare to other weight function of DWkNN [15], Shepard[16], Duhani[14], Inverse rule of Duhani[14], uniform function [17] as k values increase. For glass dataset, there are 7 classes and 214 instances. This all instances taken as a training and testing set and error rate is calculated. Same for Ionosphere has 2 classes, 351 instances and vehicle has 4 classes, 946 instances.

Dataset	k	DW kNN	Shepard Rule	Duhani	Inverse Rule	Uniform kNN	Proposed kNN
Glass	10	0.2570	0.2944	0.3084	0.3410	0.3645	0.2523
	100	0.2850	0.2944	0.3738	0.3692	0.4019	0.2570
	200	0.3037	0.2944	0.5421	0.3738	0.5561	0.2570
IonoSphere	53	0.1396	0.1282	0.1852	0.1823	0.1994	0.1282
	100	0.1538	0.1282	0.2536	0.2593	0.3020	0.1282
	150	0.1595	0.1282	0.3219	0.3134	0.3504	0.1282
Vehicle	90	0.3310	0.3310	0.3629	0.3310	0.3806	0.3286
	120	0.3322	0.3310	0.3723	0.3310	0.3913	0.3310

Table -2 Error rate Comparison with respect to different k

B. Experiment Chart:

As shown in chart of figure 2, it represents weight values for all different weight algorithms for top 10 data objects for k=10. As chart represent double weighted proposed algorithm provide smoother path compare to others, give more accurate result. Same in another chart in figure 4, top 7 data weight selected for k=100 and show that proposed algorithm has more smooth path. Other results for different dataset with different k value are shown in figure 4.

Figure 2 Smooth weight value graph for k=10 of glass dataset

Figure 3 Error rate for glass dataset for k=10,100,200 values

Figure 4 Smooth weight value graph for top 7 data among k=100 of glass dataset

Figure 5 Error rate for Ionosphere dataset for k=50,100,150 values

Figure 6 Error rate for Vehicle dataset for k=90,120 values

For glass dataset, different k value 10,100 and 200 are taken and it shows that error rate is less than others in each case in figure 3. Here, Error Rate means percentage of data points of test data are correctly not classified in class which are belong to exact own class label. So, misclassification rate is same as error rate. That means it is opposite of Accuracy [11]. We select Ionosphere dataset with k= 53,100 and 150 and got error rate less in compare to other algorithm shows in figure 5. Third selected dataset is vehicle, having 4 class and 946 instances. In figure 6, error rate is less than other algorithm for k=90 and 120. Therefore, we can finally summarize that proposed classifier is better than other algorithm for large dataset for large k value. It can reduce pressure of outlier for large k value in large dataset for classification as well as remove sensitivity of noise data in small k value. This classifier also decrease misclassification ratio for sparseness, noisy, ambiguous or mislabeled dataset.

CONCLUSION

In Data mining, data classification is growing area now days. There are number of classification techniques but for large dataset, k-NN is more robust and effective algorithm. But for selecting k value is major problem. if k values taken so small then if sparseness data in decision radius region then misclassification occur. And if k values taken as so large may be there are outliers comes into radius region and occur misclassification. Previous single and dual weight function reduce error rate compare to original k-NN algorithm but some error is there. As, proposed algorithm smooth his weight value for each top k data objects so accuracy is increased and error rate is decreased. Here, above result are shown comparison of error rate of all single and dual weight function with proposed algorithm. It is prove that this scheme is better for large dataset for large k value. This algorithm can be applied on more datasets as well as different areas where k-NN is used like text mining [19,20], Image processing [21] etc. in future.

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